

Identifying Dangerous Street Segments and Traffic Behavior in Athens using Telematics, Crash and Traffic data

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Introduction

- Road traffic crashes cause **~1.19M deaths** annually (WHO 2023), with Greece among the highest in urban EU fatality rates.
- **Behavioral Risk Factors:** Aggressive driving behaviors significantly increase crash risk, especially on dense urban roads.
- **Data-Driven Opportunity:** Integrating telematics, crash records, and traffic data enables proactive identification of high-risk segments and targeted safety interventions.

Data Overview (1/2)

- **Crash dataset** that was captured by the police and maintained by ELSTAT (2017-2022)
- Mobile **telematics data** originates from OSeven Telematics
 - Harsh Acceleration
 - Harsh Braking
 - Approx. 25,000 such events were recorded across 6,763 distinct trips
- **Fusion** via OpenStreetMap
 - Crash counts were aggregated and then joined with known intersection geometries
 - Harsh events were geolocated and aggregated to the corresponding street segment

Data Overview (2/2)

- Historical **traffic data** from TomTom Traffic API, covering a recent three-month observation period
 - Average speed (km/h)
 - Traffic Delay (seconds)
 - Travel Time (seconds)

Table 1: Descriptives of traffic data

name	Travel Time(s)				Traffic Delay(s)			Average Speed(km/h)				Length(m)
	min	mean	max	std	mean	max	std	min	mean	max	std	
Athinon	51.0	96.7	639.0	45.52	11.19	515.0	42.36	5.55	37.69	62.89	10.85	900.0
Akadimias	175.0	350.41	1423.0	135.15	54.53	729.0	105.28	4.98	15.58	27.67	4.83	1339.0
Alexandras	59.0	138.65	1005.0	78.76	11.85	853.0	43.94	3.51	18.55	32.46	3.7	660.0
Vas. Sofias	226.0	431.72	1249.0	149.36	54.85	747.0	101.31	5.21	14.03	24.12	4.12	1526.0
Vouliagmenis	54.0	86.93	701.0	28.46	1.97	612.0	21.49	4.53	39.1	60.27	8.07	895.0
Ilioupoleos	86.0	170.66	770.0	86.13	23.09	452.0	63.27	5.05	20.24	34.53	5.48	841.0
Kifisias	76.0	176.94	747.0	66.99	40.28	643.0	67.54	4.0	24.38	60.89	10.28	1055.0
Panepistimiou	106.0	237.69	1469.0	139.95	54.34	1104.0	110.62	3.02	18.71	34.91	6.26	1053.0

Objectives

- **Identify High-Risk Urban Segments:** Integrate telematics data, official crash records, and traffic data to pinpoint dangerous street segments in Athens
- Develop a metric that combines **crash frequency** with **surrogate safety measures** (harsh acceleration/braking) to better normalize crash risk.
- **Quantify relationships** between **aggressive driving events**, **crash occurrences**, and **traffic flow** conditions to guide targeted safety interventions

Methodology

- **Harsh Event Ratio:** $HER_i = \frac{H_i}{P_i}$, where:
 - H_i : harsh events recorded on street segment i
 - P_i : total number of telematics observations recorded on segment i
- **Adjusted Crash Scoring** due to absence of actual traffic volume
 - $ACS_i = C_i \times HER_i$, where C_i total number of crashes on segment i
- Define **risky hotspots** based on ACS and investigate traffic flow based on TomTom data

Dangerous Street Segments

- ACS metric ranks the most **high-risk** road segments in the Athens metropolitan area
- Reflects both the **frequency** and **severity** of traffic incidents
- **Goal:** Investigate further a subset of the risky segments that traffic data are available (n=8)

Harsh Event Ratio by Hour

- The Harsh Event Ratio (HER) rises during both morning and evening rush hours
- A pronounced spike around 17:00–18:00, likely reflecting post-work fatigue and frustration that amplify abrupt braking and acceleration

Average Speed by Hour

- Akadimias HER peak was between 17:00 – 18:00
- Vouliagmenis HER was higher between 17:00 – 18:00

Average Speed vs HER

- At **low speeds** (~10-15 km/h), the HER is relatively **high**
- At **moderate speeds** (~18-20 km/h), the ratio drops to its **lowest values**
- At **highest speeds** (~28-34 km/h), the HER **increases** again

Discussion

- Combined **crash records**, **smartphone telematics** to rank Athens's street segments by crash risk using the introduced **ACS metric** and analyze traffic flow on the risky segments
- The observed peak in harsh driving behaviors during rush hours suggests that congestion not only affects flow but also influences driver behavior
- Harsh events may reflect adaptive or defensive driving rather than unsafe practices

Conclusions

- A multi-source framework and the Adjusted Crash Score (ACS) to rank high-risk segments citywide and analyze a complete-data subset
- Harsh-event peaks during morning/evening congestion and traffic metrics (speed, delay, travel time) can prioritize targeted, proactive countermeasures
- Harsh events not solely represent unsafe conduct but also defensive driving in complex urban conditions

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